

THE THERMAL-EXPANSIVE GROWTH OF PREBREAKDOWN STREAMERS IN LIQUIDS

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Abstract

The growth of electrically conductive, low-density regions has been observed in dielectric breakdown in a variety of liquids. This phenomenon motivates the development of the present theory for coupling thermal effects with fluid mechanical effects in the dynamics of elongated, impulsively-driven bubbles. The model explicitly describes the time-dependent dimensions of a growing ellipsoidal bubble. The parameters of the model are the external pressure in the liquid, the density of energy which is deposited impulsively in the liquid, and the length over which energy is deposited.

In previous work we have developed a model for such effects associated with the growth of a bubble about an arc in a liquid [6]. In the case of the prebreakdown streamer, the geometry is not as simple as for an arc and the evolution of the bubble is found in ellipsoidal coordinates. The effect of pressure is to shorten the time scale of the bubble dynamics. Even in the case when the bubble may not be spatially resolved, the time to recollapse can be established from visual data. Calculations based on the model are shown to be consistent with experimental results on the collapse of the streamer.

Introduction

Several investigators have studied the growth of the low density, bubble-like regions (LDRs) which appear during dielectric breakdown in liquids [1,2,3]. These transient structures typically are highly branched dendrites. During the slow-growing phase they are composed of many connected, linear components which (depending on their length, the density of energy which is deposited, and the ambient pressure in the liquid) may grow to a spherical shape or remain highly elliptical. In hydrocarbon liquids the effect of elevated ambient pressure may be to suppress altogether the expansion transverse to the principal direction of streamer growth.

The parameter calculated in this paper is the time from onset to collapse of an evolving elliptical bubble. The use of this parameter is new. The calculated value of the parameter is compared to a measured value and the two are seen to be consistent. The calculation is based on an analysis of the bubble dynamics driven by the exchange of thermal and kinetic energy at the bubble surface. The resulting ordinary differential equation, which describes the evolution, is solved numerically to find the time to collapse and the maximum size of the bubble. For purposes of the analysis it is assumed that the bubble shape evolves through a family of confocal ellipsoids of revolution. This family is described naturally using prolate spheroidal coordinates.

The model explicitly allows for the variation of the ambient pressure, a parameter which has been studied in previous experiments. The present model expands the use of the pressure as a diagnostic to those cases in which the application of pressure may only diminish the time for bubble dynamics, rather than suppress entirely the slowly growing streamer. Thermodynamic properties of the material including a modified heat of vaporization and the surface tension are incorporated. These may be combined to estimate a length scale for the minor axis of a vapor bubble in equilibrium. It is shown that in vaporization induced bubbles the surface energy is a small part of the total energy.

This note derives in a general fashion the model from the assumption that the system is not dissipative. The thermodynamics of the vapor bubble are described and compared to previous experimental work. Finally, the effects of pressure are computed and the length and energy scales which may be inferred are compared to those determined from the purely thermodynamic argument. The analysis given here in 'natural' coordinates is not complete. For the micro-analysis of breakdown one must couple the charge dynamics of the ellipsoidal bubble with the hydrodynamics and thermodynamics by means of a complete energy function.

Theory: Geometry, Kinematics, and Dynamics

The motion of an incompressible liquid driven by the piston-like expansion of an ellipsoidal interface can, in the problem at hand, be described entirely by the motion of the major axis. In this section we derive a second order differential equation (4) for the 'North Pole' of the ellipsoids. The differential equation which we obtain can be used to determine the scaling of the time period as a function of the ambient pressure, the density of the liquid, and the length of the streamer. The model is a generalization for ellipsoidal bubbles of the model for spherical bubbles presented by Batchelor [4]. This model naturally introduces the length scale associated with the streamer during the initial energy deposition.

Geometry: The fundamental simplifying hypothesis of this model is that the evolving bubbles are in a family of confocal ellipsoids of revolution. The heating of the liquid occurs over the smallest of these, in a region which is taken to be close to cylindrical. In this analysis we use prolate spheroidal coordinates (ξ, η, ϕ) [5], see Figure 1. Suppose that the foci are at $x=y=0, z=\pm a/2$. In terms of the distances, r_1 and r_2 , from a point (x,y,z) to the foci:

$$\xi = (r_1 + r_2)/a,$$

$$\eta = (r_1 - r_2)/a, \text{ and}$$

$$\phi = \arctan(y/x).$$

The coordinate variables have the ranges $\xi \geq 1, -1 \leq \eta \leq 1, \text{ and } 0 \leq \phi < 2\pi$.

Figure 1: The prolate spheroidal coordinate system.[5] The ellipses, ξ -constant, and the hyperbolae, η -constant, are confocal. The ϕ coordinate is an angle of rotation and is not shown. The foci at the ends of the solid line segment have Euclidean coordinates $x=y=0$, $z=\pm a/2$.

The integrals below employ the metrical coefficients:

$$h_{\xi} = \frac{a}{2} \left(\frac{\xi^2 - \eta^2}{(\xi^2 - 1)} \right)^{1/2},$$

$$h_{\eta} = \frac{a}{2} \left(\frac{\xi^2 - \eta^2}{(1 - \eta^2)} \right)^{1/2}, \text{ and}$$

$$h_{\phi} = \frac{a}{2} \left((\xi^2 - 1)(1 - \eta^2) \right)^{1/2}.$$

Each confocal ellipse is a surface of constant ξ . Where possible we describe the bubble in terms of its semi-major and semi-minor axes, $R(t)$ and $r(t)$. In the fundamental equation (4) for the dynamics we use the normalized semi-major axis: $\Xi(t) = 2R(t)/a$. R and r are related by

$$R^2 = \left(\frac{a}{2}\right)^2 + r^2.$$

Kinematics: The kinematics of the flow field are specified by incompressibility, irrotationality, and the requirement that the bubble evolve through the family of confocal ellipses. The velocity field exactly satisfying this last condition arises as the gradient of a potential, $\Phi(t)$, which has the form

$$\Phi(\xi, \eta, t) = \alpha(t) \log \left| \frac{\xi + 1}{\xi - 1} \right|.$$

The direction of flow is everywhere normal to the ellipsoids of constant ξ . The flow speed, u , is related to the major semi-axis of the bubble, $\Xi(t)$, and to its polar velocity, $\Xi'(t)$, by:

$$u(\xi, \eta, t) = \frac{a}{2} \Xi'(t) \left\{ \Xi^2 - 1/3 \right\} \left\{ (\xi^2 - \eta^2)(\xi^2 - 1) \right\}^{-1/2} \quad (1)$$

The choice of $\alpha(t)$ is made by requiring that there be a fixed rate of mass flow, $4\pi\rho(a/2)^3 \Xi'(\Xi^2 - 1/3)$, independent of ξ .

In what follows we need the volume, $V(t) = \frac{4}{3}\pi R r^2$, and the surface area, $A(t) = 2\pi(r^2 + rR\Xi \arcsin \frac{1}{\Xi})$. For bubbles with a high aspect ratio $\Xi \approx 1$ and $A \approx 2\pi r^2 + \pi^2 rR$ giving a surface area to volume ratio $A/V \approx 3\pi/4r$.

Dynamics: The bubble evolves so that the time rate of change in the kinetic energy of the liquid, $K'(t)$, is equal to the rate at which work is done by the expanding bubble, $W'(t)$. These quantities are defined by

$$K(t) = \frac{\rho}{2} \int_{\xi \geq \Xi} u^2 dV.$$

Integrating the expression using u as given in (1) yields:

$$K(t) = 4\pi\rho \left(\frac{a}{2}\right)^5 (\Xi')^2 f(\Xi) \quad \text{in which}$$

$$f(\Xi) = (\Xi^2 - 1/3)^2 \log |(\Xi+1)/(\Xi-1)|. \quad (2)$$

and ρ is the liquid density.

It is assumed that there is no heat conduction to the exterior, (adiabatic hypothesis). The rate at which K is changing is equal to the rate of work by the normal force at the bubble boundary and at a material ellipsoidal surface 'at infinity'. The pressure interior to the bubble is taken to be uniform; that at infinity is the ambient pressure, p_{∞} . Thus, the power is:

$$\begin{aligned} W'(t) &= p(t, \Xi) V'(t, \Xi) - \lim_{\xi \rightarrow \infty} p(t, \xi) V'(t, \xi) \\ &= (p(t) - p_{\infty}) V'(t), \\ &= \frac{4\pi}{3} \left(\frac{a}{2}\right)^3 (p - p_{\infty}) (3\Xi^2 - 1) \Xi'. \quad (3) \end{aligned}$$

Equating K' and W' , one derives the following equation for Ξ'' :

$$\begin{aligned} f(\Xi)\Xi'' &= \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{2}{a}\right)^2 \left\{ \frac{p - p_{\infty}}{\rho} \right\} (3\Xi^2 - 1) - \\ &(\Xi')^2 (3\Xi^2 - 1) \left\{ 6\Xi \log \left| \frac{\Xi+1}{\Xi-1} \right| - (3\Xi^2 - 1)/(\Xi^2 - 1) \right\} \quad (4) \end{aligned}$$

This is the fundamental equation for the motion of the major axis of the ellipsoid. Because $f(\Xi)$ is positive and differentiable, this differential equation has a solution which, for various initial conditions of interest, we solve numerically using Gear's method for stiff systems [7]. To obtain a solution, the pressure within the bubble is taken to be uniform and,

according to the adiabatic hypothesis, $p(t) V^{\gamma}(t)$ is constant (here γ is the adiabatic exponent of the gas.) The constant value is set at $t=0$ based on measured or estimated values of the energy density, ϵ_0 , and the initial volume, $V(0)$. For reasons

discussed below, the surface energy is ignored without introducing appreciable error into the solution. The solution to this equation yields the time evolution of the normalized major semi-axis. The time-evolution of the minor semi-axis of the bubble, $r(t)$, is shown in Figure 3.

Application

In the selection of the initial values it is necessary to partition the energy. The energy in the bubble, H , before there is any appreciable transfer of momentum to the liquid (i.e. with $\Xi'=0$) is:

$$H_0 = (p_0 - p_\infty)V_0 + \lambda\rho V_0 + \tau A_0.$$

Here, λ is the heat in the vapor at the phase transition. It includes the heat to elevate the fluid to the boiling point and the heat of vaporization. In water, λ changes by less than 5% between 0.1 and 10.0 MPa. By contrast, in hexane and toluene λ increases by 25% as the pressure increases from 0.1 to 0.8 MPa. The surface tension, τ , in water-vapor interfaces is of order .7 N/m. For both water and several hydrocarbon liquids the dominant term in the present discussion is the second one.

One of the distinctive features of the growth of the prebreakdown structures is the creation of a nucleation site in which surface tension is probably not a dominant mechanism. For water

$$\lambda \approx 3 \times 10^3 \text{ kJ/kg and the ratio}$$

$\tau A / \lambda \rho V$ is about 10^{-9} m/r. Thus, the surface energy is comparable to the energy of vaporization in ellipsoidal bubbles when the cross-section has a radius of about 10^{-9} m. The fact that the slow growing streamer is detectible optically shows that it must be several orders of magnitude larger than the sub-micron size, above. Correspondingly, the surface energy must be several orders of magnitude less than the vaporization energy.

Figure 2: High speed photographs of prebreakdown streamers in water. The sequence is from lower left to upper right progressing through the columns with 0.5 μ s between frames. The ambient pressure is 8.7 MPa. Note the collapsing of the stem behind the growing streamer. The model presented in this paper considers the dynamics of a single branch in the bushy structure.

Table I: Period of the bubble dynamics as a function of p_∞ .

Pressure (MPa)	Period (μ s)
.101	79.0
1.01	11.6
8.7	2.0

It has been observed that pressure suppresses streamer growth and the current pulses which accompany the growth. In hydrocarbons the effect is seen as a sharply defined extinction above certain pressures. In water there is no such extinction to pressures above 10.0 MPa. However, the slow growing streamer does produce a bubble which collapses in less than 5 μ s. The photographic evidence for this is seen in Figure 2. The sequence of frames is from lower left to upper right progressing through the columns. The frames show the growth of the LDR due to a single voltage pulse. Behind the growing structure there is a collapse of the LDR. Although the width of the structure can not be directly estimated from the photo, knowing the interframe time to be 0.5 μ s allows one to establish the upper bound on the recollapse time. This rapid event is not seen at 0.1 or at 1.0 MPa.

The model has been employed to calculate the time history of the growth and the time scale for collapse in water at three ambient pressures. We have employed estimates of the charge injection volume using injection length, $a = 200 \mu$ m, a minor semi-axis of 7 μ m, and an energy deposition density 1% greater than the specific energy of the vapor phase, λ , as above. The minor semi-axis is chosen to be about the size indicated in [3]. Table 1 shows the pressure dependence of the time to recollapse. One of the distinctive features of these bubbles is that the interior pressure does not fall to a value much below the ambient pressure. This complicates the analysis of the dependence on the ambient pressure, p_∞ .

Finally, Figure 3 shows the time trace of the growing minor semi-axis at 8.7 MPa. The initial conditions are as above. The initial velocity of the bubble is 0.

Summary

We have presented a model for the study of micro-bubbles. It considers bubbles of elliptical shape and generalizes one presented earlier for spherical bubbles. The novel features are the initial energy deposition in a finite cylindrical region and the application to prebreakdown streamers. The model accounts for the rapid recollapse at elevated ambient pressures and introduces the period of the bubble motion as a new parameter for experimental study. The model does not attempt to include the effects of the charge distribution and currents which drive the bubble mechanics. Kelley and Hebner [3] and Pace, et al. (contribution A-4 to this conference) have investigated the current pulses which discharge in the LDR. The inclusion of electro-dynamic effects in our model requires information about the electrical conductivity of the region on and near the surface of the bubble.

Figure 3: The time evolution of the minor semi-axis of the bubble with ambient pressure 8.7 Mpa. Initial conditions of the bubble are major semi-axis, $R = 200 \mu\text{m}$, minor semi-axis, $r = 7 \mu\text{m}$, and energy density, $\epsilon_0 = 3.03 \times 10^3 \text{ kJ/kg}$.

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